

Deep exploration BoostEd by Advanced exploration Technologies

Quality Management Plan

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Deliverable	1.1
Summary	The DeepBEAT's project quality management plan is established to define the framework for formal quality management. The operations team, including the coordination team and work package leaders, will set key performance indicators to evaluate different aspects of overall performance. Regular assessments will ensure continuous monitoring and evaluation of these indicators.
Version:	1
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1. Project Scope and Objectives

1.1. General description

The DeepBEAT project is developing innovative and sustainable technologies for the discovery of deep-seated mineral resources, particularly in complex geological environments. To achieve this goal, the project is addressing several key challenges in its objectives:

The **development of advanced geochemical methods** is being promoted by DeepBEAT to optimize the detection and interpretation of signals of deep-seated mineralization, even under challenging conditions. This includes the refinement of measurement methods to enhance their speed, precision, and cost-effectiveness, ensuring their applicability across diverse geological settings.

Another key aspect of the project is the **geochemical characterization and 3D modelling** of subsurface structures. By integrating geochemical surface and core drill data with geophysical information, DeepBEAT generates Artificial Intelligence (AI)-supported 3D models. These models offer valuable insights into concealed mineral deposits and contribute to a more comprehensive understanding of the formation and location of ore bodies.

A core element of the project is the **minimization of environmental impact**. DeepBEAT emphasizes sustainable, environmentally friendly exploration methods that minimize ecological disruption, including techniques that reduce intervention in natural habitats while enabling the discovery of raw materials.

In order to **reduce exploration costs and enhance data collection**, DeepBEAT is developing faster and more efficient sampling techniques. These include the use of drones in hard-to-reach areas, enhanced real-time data collection, and the application of AI for analysing large datasets. These advancements not only reduce costs but also accelerate decision-making in mineral exploration.

To enhance exploration efficiency, a **workflow** is being developed that combines previous points. The transition from conventional 2D methods to state-of-the-art 3D approaches enhances the accuracy of resource estimates, enabling more informed decisions for future mining activities.

DeepBEAT also places great emphasis on **public engagement and education**, promoting responsible exploration and actively involving local communities in the process. Through information campaigns, public events, and educational initiatives, awareness is raised about the importance of raw materials in modern society as well as the perspectives of the affected communities are also heard and respected.

Ultimately, DeepBEAT contributes to **increasing the EU's strategic autonomy** by promoting domestic extraction of critical raw materials (CRMs). This supports the European goal of reducing dependency on third countries and strengthening the resource base within the EU.

1.2. Project's Work package structure

The DeepBEAT project consists of five interactive work packages (WPs, see Figure 1). WP1 focuses on project management and coordination. WPs 2, 3, and 4 are dedicated to developing exploration techniques, each linked to a specific test site. Within these WPs, tasks are organized to characterize deposits, mineral systems, and create prospectivity models; test and improve modern geochemical analysis methods; involve mathematical developments for geochemical data handling and targeted sampling; deals with sampling and testing new surface media as well as integrate all findings into a comprehensive workflow. WP5 addresses Exploitation, Dissemination, and Communication, collaborating closely with WPs 1-4.

Figure 1: WP structure of DeepBEAT. The use of the same colour in technical WP2-4 indicates that tasks (T) in general are reaching over the 3 WPs, while still considering the individual requirements for the deposit. WP1 and 5 is overarching WP2-4. T5.2 emphasizes the community engagement of the three sites

1.3. Key project deliverables and milestones

Deliverables and Milestones are essential to DeepBEAT's successful implementation, ensuring optimized geochemical methods, AI-supported 3D modeling, and efficient, cost-effective exploration while prioritizing sustainability and active public engagement. The following list shows the Deliverables (Table 1) and Milestones (Table 2). The most significant of these, in relation to the objectives of the project, are highlighted.

Table 1: List of Deliverables in the EU project DeepBEAT, highlighting the most significant ones for the project objectives.

No	Deliverable Name	Lead Partner	Type	Dissemination Level	Due Date
D1.1	Quality Plan	HZDR	R	PU	31-03-2025
D1.2	Data Management Plan	HZDR	DMP	PU	31-12-2024
D2.1	VMS mineral system characterization and deposit model	GTK	R	PU	30-09-2025
D2.2	Analytical protocols	QUC	R	PU	31-03-2026
D2.3	UAV assisted sampling protocol	GTK	R	PU	31-01-2027
D2.4	Multi-sensor analysis and data fusion	IMA	DEM	SEN	31-03-2027
D3.1	Report on data and preliminary 3D model for granite hosted Li/Sn/W deposits	BEAK	R	SEN	30-09-2025
D3.2	Compositional calibration	HZDR	OTHER	PU	30-09-2026
D3.3	Report on the completed Erzgebirge/Krušné hory 3D model and AI-based PM	BEAK	R	SEN	31-03-2027
D3.4	Report on the new methodologies and application tests	BEAK	R	PU	30-09-2027
D4.1	Overview of alkaline metasomatite related REE-Zr-(Mo) mineral system	CGS	R	PU	30-09-2027
D4.2	Variance based sampling	HZDR	DEM	PU	30-06-2027
D4.3	Workflow for geochemical exploration of deep seated deposits	QUC	R	PU	31-07-2027
D5.1	DCE	LC	R	SEN	31-03-2025
D5.2	MDCE	LC	R	SEN	31-05-2026
D5.3	FDCE	LC	R	SEN	30-09-2027
D5.4	Training material	LC	R	PU	30-09-2027

Table 2: List of Milestones in the EU project DeepBEAT, highlighting the most significant ones for the project objectives.

No	Milestone Name	Lead Partner	Due Date
M1.1	Kick off meeting	HZDR	31-12-2024
M1.2	Former and ongoing activities with synergies to DeepBEAT identified	LC	31-03-2026
M2.1	Completion of 3D geological model of Saramäki	GTK	30-09-2025
M2.2	Tree crown and species classification maps at Saramäki	GTK	31-12-2025
M2.3	Results of preliminary biogeochemical sampling campaign analysed	GTK	31-05-2026
M2.4	Operational multi-sensor analysis platform	IMA	31-05-2026
M2.5	Generic concept for geochemical mineral exploration	HZDR	31-07-2025
M3.1	Sampling strategy defined	HZDR	30-09-2025
M3.2	Data fusion established	UL	31-01-2026
M3.3	Final 3D model completed	BEAK	30-09-2026
M3.4	Report on surficial geochemistry in Erzgebirge/Krušné hory	BEAK	30-11-2026
M4.1	Preliminary regional scale 3D model for Hůrky	CGS	30-06-2026
M4.2	Application of isotopic techniques for exploration of alkaline metasomatite REE-Zr-(Mo) mineralization	QUC	30-09-2026
M4.3	Prognosticated resources for selected part of Hůrky reference site	CGS	30-06-2027
M4.4	Stratification of the area as input for spatial sampling strategy	CGS	31-07-2025
M4.5	Exploratory compositional data analysis completed	HZDR	31-03-2026
M4.6	Mo and Na as mobile tracer for metasomatic REE deposits in surface media samples	QUC	31-07-2027
M5.1	Webpage	LC	31-12-2024
M5.2	Community engagement event	LC	31-05-2025
M5.3	Final list of Key Exploitable Results available with clear ownership	LC	30-09-2027

2. Project Management and Governance

2.1. Project management approach description

Project management encompasses all essential activities to ensure the successful completion of the project within the technical and financial framework outlined in the Grant Agreement. Lead by HZDR, WP1 is responsible for managing and coordinating the project, ensuring alignment with its scope, budget, resources, and quality standards.

Any amendments or optimizations are discussed collaboratively with all relevant partners, with decisions made through mutual agreement. Effective internal communication is crucial

to ensure that information reaches the right stakeholders and that decisions are made efficiently and on time.

Quality management establishes key quality control and assurance measures to foster effective collaboration among consortium partners and ensure the successful delivery of project results. Additionally, risk management provides the necessary processes and techniques to assess and mitigate potential project risks, with a focus on proactive identification and response strategies.

2.2. Structure

The organizational framework of DeepBEAT comprises the General Assembly, the Executive Board, the Advisory Board, the Project Coordination Team, and the Communication and Dissemination Team.

The General Assembly is the highest decision-making body, responsible for making decisions on overall management and strategic matters. It includes one representative from each beneficiary. A deputy was appointed for each beneficiary. The composition of the General Assembly can be seen in Annex A2: Composition of the General Assembly.

The Executive Board, made up of WP leaders and project lead, is responsible for overseeing the daily operations of the project and assessing its progress. Board members have voting rights on internal decisions regarding activities, provided they attend all meetings. As the supervisory body, the Executive Board ensures the proper execution of the project, managing its daily activities and reporting to the General Assembly. A deputy is appointed for each WP leader. The composition of the Executive Board can be seen in Annex A3: Composition of the Executive Board.

The Advisory Board monitors the progress of research and supports the successful involvement of the community integration in the project, as well as the scientific and technical excellence, ensuring the highest quality and impact of the project. The Advisory Board is a team of leading independent experts from research and industry from Europe in fields of mineral exploration, geosciences, sustainability, critical thinking and communication. The composition of the Advisory Board can be seen in Annex A4: Composition of the Advisory Board.

The Coordination Team (HZDR) consists of the Scientific Lead, Project Coordinators, EU Office Liaison, and Financial Coordinator(s). This team is responsible for communication with the European Commission as well as internal stakeholder communication (Consortium).

The Communication, Dissemination and Exploitation (CDE) Team (LC) is responsible for dissemination, outreach, and impact. This team will handle all communications with external stakeholders and manage Intellectual Property Rights (IPR).

3. Management Processes and Tools

3.1. Meetings

The project includes various types of meetings to ensure effective collaboration, coordination, and decision-making among all partners.

Consortium Meetings are multi-day events held twice a year, bringing together the entire consortium, representatives from the European Commission, and other necessary stakeholders for the success of the project. The spring meeting is conducted online, while the autumn meeting is held in person at different partner locations.

General Assembly Meetings take place alongside the Consortium Meetings or, if necessary, unscheduled for urgent decisions.

The **Executive Board Meeting** meets approximately every three months in a virtual format. It is also possible to convene at short notice in cases of emergency.

WP Meetings are scheduled monthly, except for a summer break in July due to overlapping vacation periods across partner organizations. Participants include all individuals actively working in the WP, as well as partners and associated partners affected by the WP.

Task Meetings are organized internally within each WP as required. They involve the individuals working directly on the respective task.

Topic Meetings focus on cross-WP tasks and are organized as needed. The composition of each Topic Meeting is determined based on the individuals impacted by the specific topic. The Executive Board has identified five key topics:

- Mineralisation System Characterisation
- Distal Footprint
- Sampling Strategy
- Geochemistry
- Workflow

3.2. Publication procedure & guidelines

Publications (e.g. deliverables, manuscripts, abstracts, etc.) are compiled by the author(s) from the task(s) or work package(s). The first author takes the leading role in the planning, task allocation and communication with the reviewers as well as the submission (with the exception of the deliverable process). The review process is primarily conducted by the Executive Board. The Executive Board may appoint additional project internal reviewers as re-

quired. The author(s) will consider the feedback and editing the publication before submission. The workflow for quality assessment of the publication and the corresponding timeframes are illustrated in Figure 2.

Figure 2: The overall publication procedure and responsibilities in the DeepBEAT project. Additional steps for Deliverables are marked in orange. Following abbreviations were used: R – Reminder, CDE – Communication, Dissemination and Exploitation, EU – European, DL – Deadline, wk – weeks, w/d – Working days..

In the case of a **Deliverable**, several additional elements have to be considered (marked in orange in Figure 2). The Coordinator Team will send reminders to the lead of the responsible work package of the deliverable or, if known, to the first author. In order to ensure a standardized format, it is essential that the deliverables follow the template provided by the coordinator team based on the DeepBEAT corporate design. The first author is responsible for forwarding the finalized version to the coordinator team a minimum of three working days prior to the submission deadline. The coordinator team is responsible for submitting the deliverables.

3.3. Reporting to the European Commission

The Coordinator Team is the primary contact with the European Commission (EC) and is responsible for reporting to the EC on the proper use of the budget and resources. This includes regular progress updates to the Project Officer, preparing reports for each reporting period,

and providing support to partners. The Project Coordinator Team also ensures the timely submission of deliverables or communicates any delays and deviations in advance, as well as justifies and implements any necessary amendment requests.

4. Quality Management in DeepBEAT

4.1. Organisation and implementation

Progress monitoring and quality assurance will be implemented at various hierarchical levels, ultimately converging at the Executive Board. The board establish quality management tools and ensure that each responsible partner efficiently and promptly fulfills their monitoring, reporting, and feedback obligations within the work packages. These appointments, as well as regular updates, are documented in the Executive Board meeting minutes to ensure compliance with project standards and the establishment of effective feedback channels.

The quality aspects include compliance with data protection regulations, quality assurance/quality control of both legacy and newly acquired data, quality of communication, and the quality of produced results, among others.

4.2. Key Performance Indicators

The Key Performance Indicators (KPI) will be monitored during the project and used to guide internal decision-making. A list of DeepBEAT’s KPIs can be find in Table 3.

Table 3: List of Key Performance Inidcators (KPI) in the DeepBEAT project.

KPI No.	KPI Description	KPI Lead
1	Prospectivity models based on data fusion and on (AI-supported) 3D models for three test sites	
2	Two Triple Quadrupole Inductively Coupled Plasma Mass Spectrometry (TQ-ICP-MS) measurement protocols provided for the mafic volatile element suite, one for plant and one for soil matrices. These protocols will also be adaptable to isotope measurements	QUC
3	An R package as open-source code for compositional calibration	HZDR
4	Reduce the time required for sampling and data acquisition by around half while maintaining the same information density and data quality	
5	Three community engagement events arranged, one per each testsite; public consultations and surveys conducted	LC
6	>2000 interactions in social media, 2 videos	LC
7	A workflow for 3D mineral prospectivity mapping including social aspects, tested on three test sites	
8	Ten innovative technologies, applicable on different ecological settings	All

9	Two detailed characterizations of deposits based on drill cores	CGS, GTK
10	Introduce new calibration method accelerating measurements by at least 15%	
11	Provide for all items in the final workflow a European solution (for each major step there is a service provider in Europe)	
12	Test three new ultra-low impact surface media for exploration	
13	Trainings and webinars on UNFC classification	HZDR
14	18 open access publications	All
15	12 presentations, 10 posters	All
16	Participation in 2 clustering events	All
17	5 webinars/short courses/training	All
18	1 workshop, at least 50 participants	LC
19	1 workshop in UL, 15 students can benefit from these examples each year	UL
20	Website: at least 6.000 visits in total during the project	LC
21	Social media: >300 followers, >2.000 interactions and shares in social media in total during the project.	LC
22	Visual material: leaflets and brochure printed, 1 animated video, 1 video on YouTube, 2 factsheets, 6 press releases and interviews presented	LC
23	18 publications	All
24	6 press releases during the project	LC
25	8 articles for media distribution	
26	Participation on 3 outreach events	HZDR

4.3. Quality Management Tools

Ensuring high standards in project execution requires a structured approach to quality management. In the DeepBEAT project, several quality tools are implemented to monitor performance, manage risks, and maintain transparency. These tools help streamline processes, enhance collaboration, and ensure compliance with project objectives.

At the foundation of these efforts is the **Quality Management Plan (D1.1)**, which establishes formal quality guidelines from the outset. The Executive Board defined key performance indicators and quality management tools to evaluate project effectiveness. Regular assessments allow for continuous monitoring and necessary adjustments to maintain high standards.

A key element is the **Data Management Plan (D1.2)**, which ensures proper handling of data from various partners while promoting open knowledge sharing. Intellectual Property Rights (IPR). The data management is integrated into project management, with regular reviews every 6 months to ensure continuous improvement.

To address potential risks, a **Contingency Plan** is in place, managed by the Executive Board. Risk estimation and anticipation are regular agenda points in board meetings, allowing for

early identification and rapid mitigation planning. This proactive approach ensures that challenges are addressed swiftly and efficiently.

The **Dissemination, Communication, and Exploitation Plan** (D5.1) focuses on ensuring effective communication and knowledge dissemination. It includes structured reporting, such as a midterm (D5.2) and final report (D5.3), to track progress and maximize project impact.

To systematically track project progress, the Executive Board compiles a internal **Process Status Report** on a quarterly basis. This report provides an overview of ongoing research activities, the remaining deliverables and milestones, and an evaluation of KPIs. The regular updates by the Executive Board enables it to proactively address potential risks and ensure smooth project execution. The Process Status Report is structured in the form of a table, offering a clear and transparent overview of project developments. Access to this report is available to all partners within the consortium, ensuring that everyone is informed about current progress, deadlines, and performance assessments. This approach fosters collaboration and enables timely interventions if necessary, contributing to the overall success of the project.

5. Annex A1: History of Changes of the QMP document

Table 4: Table of document modifications.

Name	Affiliation	Contribution / Review	Version
Anne Wollenberg	HZDR	Initial Version	1
Maarit Middleton	GTK	Edits	1
Andreas Knobloch	BEAK	Edits	1

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6. Annex A2: Composition of the General Assembly

Table 5: Composition of the General Assembly with a list of representative of each beneficiary, including the Deputies.

Beneficiary	Responsible Person	Deputy
Project Lead	Solveig Pospiech	
HZDR	Anne Wollenberg	Sandra Birtel
BEAK	Andreas Knobloch	Roberto de la Rosa
GTK	Maarit Middleton	Hafsa Munia
CGS	Vojtech Wertich	Jan Pasava
LC	Péter Mogyorósi	Katarína Nagyová
SCI	Denise Baumann	Jochen Meurs
IMA	Damith Agampodi	Jens Johansson
UL	Jean Cauzid	Cécile Fabre
FCOY	Ilari Kinnunen	Kalle Penttilä
QUC	Matthew Leybourne	Sara Momenipour
ZL	Thomas Dittrich	Lotta Hanzelmann

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7. Annex A3: Composition of the Executive Board

Table 6: Composition of the Executive Board with a list of representative of each work package (WP), including the Deputies.

Work Package	Responsible Person	Deputy
Project Lead	Solvieg Pospiech	
WP1	Anne Wollenberg	Sandra Birtel
WP2	Andreas Knobloch	
WP3	Maarit Middleton	Hafsa Munia
WP4	Vojtech Wertich	
WP5	Katarína Nagyová	

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8. Annex A4: Composition of the Advisory Board

Name	Lluís Fontboté	Karen Hanhøj	
Organisation	Université de Genève	British Geological Survey	
Sector	Academia	Research	
Area of expertise	Mineral exploration, geoscience, sustainability	Mineral exploration, geoscience,	
Country	Switzerland	England	
Status	Confirmed	Confirmed	

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